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This article examines the implementation of Islamic financial services in microfinance organizations in Uzbekistan and compares them with international practice. The study aims to assess the institutional, legal and practical aspects of Islamic microfinance and identify opportunities and limitations for Uzbekistan. Using an analytical approach, the article studies Shariah-compliant instruments such as murabaha, ijara, mudaraba, musharaka and salam, as well as their practical mechanisms. The experience of Malaysia, Pakistan, Indonesia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan is summarized in terms of regulation, Shariah governance, institutional cooperation and consumer protection. Particular attention is paid to the authorization of Islamic financial services for microfinance organizations in Uzbekistan from 2024 and the initial activities of "Apex Moliya", "Ansor MMT" and "IMAN". The findings show that Islamic microfinance can meet demand for value-based financial services, expand financial inclusion, support small entrepreneurship and strengthen social justice. The article proposes improving the regulatory framework, integrating zakat and waqf institutions, and using fintech solutions to enhance sustainability.

Keywords: Islamic microfinance, microfinance institutions, Shariah-compliant finance, financial inclusion, Uzbekistan.

Introduction.

Microfinance organizations are an integral part of today's global financial system and play an important role in supporting the population and small businesses. The main task of microfinancing is to expand the economic activity of low-income segments of the population, improve their standard of living and stimulate entrepreneurial initiatives by providing them with financial resources. Therefore, the effective functioning of financial services in microfinance organizations plays an important role in ensuring economic development and social stability.

In recent years, the demand for Islamic financial services in the microfinance system has increased significantly. One of the main factors in this process is the preference of certain segments of the population for financial products that correspond to their religious beliefs and spiritual values. The main principles of Islamic finance – interest-free financing, limiting uncertainty and excessive risk, applying fair partnership relations, and directing funds only to halal activities – serve to ensure social responsibility and financial justice in microfinance practice.

International experience shows that Islamic financing instruments have been successfully integrated into the microfinance process in many countries. In Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan, Sudan and Bangladesh, Islamic microfinance entities have created opportunities for thousands of families to start or expand their businesses based on contracts such as murabaha, ijara, musharaka and mudaraba. These instruments demonstrate themselves as a financial solution that replaces traditional microcredit, is flexible and compliant with Sharia.

The active development of the microfinance system in Uzbekistan, the high demand of the population for financial services in accordance with Sharia law, and the possibilities of adapting international experi-

ence to local conditions make the introduction of Islamic financing an urgent issue. Also, starting from 2024, the formation of a legal framework for the provision of Islamic financial services to microfinance organizations has further increased the practical significance of this direction. From this point of view, the study of the current state of Islamic financial services in microfinance organizations, a comparative analysis of foreign experience, and the identification of promising areas for local practice determine the scientific and practical significance of this study.

Methodology.

This study is based on a combined analytical approach that integrates literature analysis, comparative analysis, content analysis and expert evaluation. At the first stage, scientific works on Islamic microfinance were reviewed in order to identify the main theoretical approaches, methodological views and practical debates in this field. The literature shows that Islamic microfinance is usually examined from two main perspectives. The first group of studies emphasizes its role in financial inclusion, poverty reduction, social justice and support for small entrepreneurship. The second group focuses on financial efficiency, institutional sustainability, risk management, limited outreach and the difficulties of applying Shariah-compliant instruments in practice. Studies by Berguiga et al. (2020), Mutia et al. (2023), Fianto and Gan (2017), Ginanjar and Kassim (2020), Kassim and Hassan (2018), Hossain et al. (2024), Mohamed and Elgammal (2023), Aziz et al. (2020) and other authors were used to identify these different scientific positions.

The literature analysis also shows that Islamic microfinance has not been studied equally across regions. While the experience of Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan and several other countries has been widely discussed, the practice of Central Asian countries remains relatively less explored. In particular, the institutional de-

velopment of Islamic microfinance in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan requires a more systematic comparative analysis. Therefore, the literature review served not only as a theoretical basis, but also as a tool for identifying research gaps and defining the analytical direction of this article.

As an empirical basis, the study used the annual reports of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024, the Regulation “On the Procedure for Providing Islamic Financing Services by Microfinance Organizations”, open data of “Apex Moliya”, “Anzor MMT” and “IMAN”, as well as official statistics and reports related to Malaysia, Pakistan, Indonesia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. The experience of these countries was compared in terms of legal regulation, institutional models, Shariah governance, financial instruments, consumer protection and integration with social finance mechanisms.

The study also applies content analysis to examine regulatory documents, institutional reports and official information on Islamic microfinance services. Qualitative and quantitative indicators were summarized through an integrated analysis. Based on this approach, the article identifies the current state of Islamic financial services in Uzbekistan’s microfinance organizations, compares it with international practice and develops practical recommendations for further improvement.

Main part.

Global Islamic microfinance still accounts for a relatively small share of the overall microfinance industry. Although it is difficult to measure the exact size of the global market due to the scattered practice of reporting, most research agrees that the field is gradually expanding due to the growing demand for Shariah-compliant financial services, Islamic lending models based on financial technologies, and the institutionalization of social finance based on zakat and waqf. However, Islamic microfinance remains much less prevalent than traditional microfinance, and its coverage varies significantly across regions.

Among all countries, Malaysia offers the most comprehensive institutional framework for Islamic microfinance, so the analysis of international experience logically begins with the Malaysian model.

Malaysian experience. Today, Malaysia is recognized as a world leader in Islamic finance. As an initial step, the country’s first fully Islamic bank – Bank Islam

Malaysia Berhad began operations through the “Islamic Banking Act” adopted in 1983. Later, this law was adapted to modern financial market requirements and replaced in 2013 with the “Islamic Financial Services Act” (IFSA 2013). IFSA 2013 designated not only prudential supervision but also compliance with Sharia as a mandatory requirement.

Some researchers believe that the legal consolidation of Islamic finance guarantees its full institutional independence (Yahya, 2019). Others, on the contrary, argue that too strict integration of Islamic finance instruments into the legal system can limit its adaptability to market conditions (El-Gamal, 2006).

In our opinion, in order to expand Islamic financial services in Uzbekistan, it is first necessary to strengthen the legislative framework, because in the absence of legal guarantees, distrust between financial institutions and clients may arise.

Islamic microfinance in Malaysia is institutionally divided into two main strata:

Official financial institutions: Bank Islam Malaysia Berhad, Bank Muamalat, Maybank Islamic, as well as state financial institutions (Agrobank, TEKUN Nasional, Amanah Ikhtiar Malaysia – AIM).

Social institutions: Zakat Councils (State Islamic Religious Councils - SIRC), Yayasan Wakaf Malaysia and other waqf organizations.

These two strata are inextricably linked by a “dual channel model”. In this case, the sources of social finance (zakat, charity, and endowment) are combined with official commercial resources. Major Islamic microfinance providers are given in the Table 1.

In our opinion, in today’s global financial system, such dual-line integration is considered the most effective model of Islamic microfinance. Because, along with financial stability, it also ensures the principles of social justice.

There are also some considerations in this regard: according to some scholars, these instruments are not economically different from traditional financial products, but are expressed only in “Islamic terminology”. However, other scholars assess that these instruments introduce the principles of “justice, stability, and humanity” into the financial system. In our opinion, by gradually introducing these instruments in Uzbekistan, it is possible not only to diversify the financial market, but also to meet the religious and moral requirements of the population.

Table 1.

Major Islamic Microfinance Providers in Malaysia: Objectives and Services		
Organization	Main Objective	Types and Features of Islamic Microfinance Services
Amanah Ikhtiar Malaysia (AIM) – established 1987, NGO microfinance institution	Supporting low-income households and women entrepreneurs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qard hasan (interest-free loans with service fee) • Group-based lending • Training and mentoring programs
TEKUN Nasional – established 1998, government-backed microfinance agency	Financing small entrepreneurs and traders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tawarruq and Qard hasan-based microfinance
Agrobank – established 1969, full-fledged Islamic bank since 2015; government development bank	Agricultural microfinance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tawarruq • Ijara • Takaful (micro-insurance) • Ar-Rahnu (Islamic pawn broking)
Bank Islam Malaysia – Bang-KIT (est. 1983)	Qard hasan and social finance-based micro-finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qard hasan • Integrated zakat and cash waqf funds • Microfinance linked with training and mentoring

Source: Compiled by the author based on official information from Amanah Ikhtiar Malaysia, TEKUN Nasional, Agrobank and Bank Islam Malaysia.

The Malaysian experience shows that the success of Islamic microfinance is based on its legislative consolidation, strict regulatory control, and close connection with social finance institutions. In our opinion, the Malaysian model can serve as an important example for Uzbekistan. However, based on our legal and institutional conditions, it is advisable to choose the path of adaptation, not direct transfer. In particular, the harmonization of zakat and waqf institutions with the state and commercial financial system, in our opinion, creates great opportunities for national economic reforms.

Pakistan's experience. Pakistan is considered to be the country with the most comprehensive micro-finance system. Currently, Pakistan is one of the leading countries in the field of microfinance, and the Akhuwat Islamic microfinance practice, which is considered a model for NGO models, also operates here. In the fight against poverty, special attention is paid to microfinance institutions (MFIs) in Pakistan, and in 2001

the government adopted a special regulatory document. According to the document adopted by the Pakistani government in 2001, people earning less than the officially established minimum income are recognized as “microfinance clients”. In addition, successful MMIs are encouraged and given tax breaks for a period of 5 years to transform them into full-fledged banks (Abdul Rahman & Dean, 2013).

For financial institutions providing Islamic micro-finance services, a comprehensive “Guidelines for Islamic Microfinance Activities for Financial Institutions” was published by the Central Bank of Pakistan in 2006 (State Bank of Pakistan, 2007). It defines four institutional models of Islamic microfinance and develops standards for them (Table 2). This guide is very comprehensive and has features that can serve as a model for other countries. The four main models envisaged in this document are as follows:

Table 2.

Four Institutional Models of Islamic Microfinance in Pakistan	
Islamic Microfinance Banks	Islamic Microfinance Services within Islamic Banks
<p>The operational scope, obligations, and minimum paid-up capital requirements for Islamic microfinance banks differ by level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National level: at least PKR 1000 million (approx. USD 11.3 million) • Provincial level: at least PKR 500 million (approx. USD 5.6 million) • Regional level: at least PKR 400 million (approx. USD 4.5 million) • District level: at least PKR 300 million (approx. USD 3.4 million). <p>In addition, appointing a Shariah Advisor is mandatory for each bank.</p>	<p>Islamic banks in Pakistan are also encouraged to provide microfinance services to low-income segments. The 2006 guidelines apply to them as well. In compliance with Shariah, banks may offer microfinance services in four ways: establishing a dedicated “micro-finance window” within existing branches, opening separate microfinance branches or using mobile banking, creating new subsidiaries, or providing financing to existing MFIs.</p>
Islamic Microfinance Services within Conventional Banks	Islamic Microfinance Services within Conventional Microfinance Banks
<p>Conventional banks are permitted to offer Islamic microfinance services if certain conditions are met, including: segregation of Islamic and interest-based</p>	<p>Conventional microfinance banks may also provide Islamic microfinance services if they meet specific regulatory criteria. The Government of Pakistan supports</p>

funds, supervision by Shariah advisors, and the establishment of an internal Shariah compliance system.

successful MFIs by granting tax exemptions for up to five years to facilitate their transition into fully licensed Islamic microfinance banks.

Source: State Bank of Pakistan, 2007.

In general, various legal norms are being developed by state authorities to ensure that microfinance, and Islamic microfinance in particular, provides wider access to low-income segments of society. At the same time, some scholars emphasize that there is no need to rush to introduce legal norms for microfinance. They believe that in countries such as Bangladesh and Indonesia, microfinance can often develop naturally without special legal frameworks (Christen, Lyman, & Rosenberg, 2003).

Akhuwat, which operates in Pakistan, is also one of the organizations that provides interest-free microfinance in the NGO model and is noteworthy for its success. The biggest difference between Akhuwat and traditional microfinance is that it operates on the basis of interest-free finance. The organization operates based on the principle of *qadr hasan* (interest-free loan), which is praised in the Holy Quran and Hadith. The main idea of Akhuwat is: "A society built on the principles of compassion and equality, where poverty is eradicated". Akhuwat's mission is: "To strengthen poor families economically and socially through interest-free microfinance, to use their entrepreneurial potential, to develop their capacity and to eliminate poverty through social orientation".

The idea of establishing Akhuwat was carried out in 2001 in Lahore as a simple charity activity and tested how interest-free microfinance could work sustainably.

Over time, donations increased far beyond the founders' expectations. By 2003, donations had reached 1.5 million rupees, and repayment of debts was 100%. As a result, it was decided to formalize Akhuwat and it was registered under the Societies Registration Act, 1860. The first branch was opened in the Township area of Lahore, and in subsequent years, with the support of the community, it was expanded to other areas.

Research shows that since Akhuwat was established, more than 3.65 million families have been financially supported through microfinance instruments (Table 3). The gender distribution in the use of the program is almost balanced, with 56 percent of loans allocated to men and 44 percent to women (Akhuwat, 2025). The total volume of loans allocated by the organization is 334.8 billion Pakistani rupees (PKR), which confirms the year-on-year growth of the scale of Akhuwat's financial activities. Currently, there are 685.6 thousand active loans, with a total portfolio of 109.2 billion rupees. The discipline of loan repayment is ensured at a high level, with a repayment rate of 99.96 percent. This indicates the financial sustainability and social credibility of the Akhuwat model. Currently, the organization operates in different regions of Pakistan and serves the population through 891 branches. This extensive network further strengthens Akhuwat's role and importance in ensuring financial inclusion.

Table 3.

Current Financial Indicators of Akhuwat

Indicator	Value
Number of supported households	3651161
Loans disbursed to male clients	3781368 (56%)
Loans disbursed to female clients	2914321 (44%)
Total disbursed financing (PKR)	334780667177
Repayment rate	99.96%
Number of active loans	685653
Current loan portfolio (PKR)	109226693127
Number of branches	891

Source: Akhuwat, 2025.

The loan repayment discipline is ensured at a high level, with a repayment rate of 99.96 percent. This reflects the financial stability and social credibility of the Akhuwat model. Currently, the organization operates in different regions of Pakistan, serving the population through 891 branches. This extensive network further strengthens the role and importance of Akhuwat in ensuring financial inclusion. In general, Akhuwat has expanded its loan volume, branches and coverage several times over the past 15 years, forming a highly disciplined microfinance model.

Pakistan is one of the leading countries in the field of microfinance, and special attention is paid to microfinance institutions in the fight against poverty. Through the legal framework created by the state, low-income populations are provided with access to finan-

cial services, and successful organizations are encouraged with additional benefits. The experience of Islamic microfinance in Pakistan has emerged as an effective model for combating poverty, based on the principles of interest-free financing, social cooperation, and responsibility.

Indonesian experience. Another widely used model in Islamic microfinance is the rural bank model. Indonesia has been successfully operating on this model. BPRSs ("Bank Perkreditasi Rakyat Syariah" – Islamic rural banks) operate here and are widespread.

Recent studies on Indonesia's rural banking sector show that the effectiveness of BPR/BPRS institutions depends on regulation, institutional governance, risk management, operational capacity, digital transformation and financial inclusion mechanisms. These factors are summarized in Figure 1 (Maradona, 2025).

Indonesia, which has been able to fulfill these conditions, has a variety of microfinance institutions: BPR (traditional rural banks), BMT (Islamic cooperatives), BPRS (Islamic rural banks) and microfinance programs

of traditional banks (Telaga & Ahmed, 2013). BPRS and BMT in particular play an important role in the expansion of Islamic microfinance.

Figure 1. Success Factors of Indonesia's Microfinance Sector

Source: Compiled by the author based on Maradona (2025).

Although the history of rural banks in Indonesia dates back many years, their formal legal regulation was carried out by a Presidential Decree in 1988. In subsequent years (1992, 1998), new decrees were issued and private rural banks were authorized to operate under the supervision of the Central Bank of Indonesia (Ahmed, 2013). On this basis, the first rural bank was established in 1989, and the first Islamic rural bank in 1991.

The main purpose of BPRS is to support the entrepreneurial activities of the poor. Their owners are usually individuals, Islamic foundations, private companies, and sometimes local governments also participate as shareholders. BPRSs under the supervision of the Central Bank have the right to accept deposits in various forms, like conventional banks (Seibel & Dwi Agung, 2006).

BPRSs divide their clients into two groups and adapt their financing methods accordingly:

– The first group is experienced and successful entrepreneurs who have been operating successfully for at least two years. They are offered products based on profit sharing, such as murabaha, musharaka, and mudaraba.

– The second group is new customers with no previous business experience. Since they are fewer in number and riskier, they are supported on the basis of a simpler product – qard hasan. The condition is that the funds should be spent on income-generating activities, not on consumption.

BPRSs have achieved rapid growth in the Islamic finance sector in Indonesia. While there were only 4 of them in the 1990s, the number of BPRSs in Indonesia has reached 173 in November 2023 (Tarmizi et al., 2024).

Figure 2. BPRS Assets, Financing, and Third-Party Funds (in trillion rupiah)

Source: Tarmizi et al., 2024.

During 2019-2023, the assets of Islamic rural banks (BPRS) in Indonesia grew steadily, with total assets increasing from IDR 13.93 trillion to IDR 23.18 trillion. During the same period, funding increased from IDR 10.18 trillion to IDR 17.03 trillion, and third-party funding increased from IDR 8.94 trillion to IDR 15.27 trillion (Figure 2). These figures indicate that Islamic finance is increasingly playing a significant role in the provision of services by the BPRS sector.

The analysis of international models determines the need for the next stage of research – to study the formation and development trends of Islamic micro-finance in the countries of Central Asia. Below, the experience of the region is analyzed in sequence.

Kazakhstani experience. The Islamic banking sector in Kazakhstan is being replenished with Islamic fintech and microfinance companies. In particular, the *Tayyab company*, launched in 2021, offers customers instant digital Islamic debit cards, as well as digital payments and money transfer services. One of the founders, D.Usponov, previously worked at the Al Saqr Islamic Leasing Company and had 15 years of banking experience. At the same time, his entrepreneurial initiative also played a major role. As Usponov noted in his interviews, it was under his leadership that Al Saqr initiated the launch of a state support program through the Kazakhstan Entrepreneurship Development Fund “Damu”. Through this initiative, Islamic finance companies were able to use state support measures for the first time. Later, Usponov developed the idea of creating a digital Islamic bank for the general public. The idea was based on the experience of the first halal bank cards in Kazakhstan, issued by Al Saqr in 2019. In just 2.5 months, 12.5 thousand cards were issued, and on some days up to 1.5 thousand applications were received (Nagimova, 2022). However, when the partner bank closed, the project stalled. Tayyab went through the StartUpBootCamp acceleration program in Dubai, where it was invested by Dubai FinTech Ventures (a partner of the Visa payment system). Later, the team returned to Kazakhstan, signed an agreement with the local RBC bank and launched a mobile application. The application was downloaded 12 thousand times in a month. Tayyab cards have restrictions in accordance with Sharia law: they cannot be used in casinos, gambling and lottery services, specialized stores selling alcohol and tobacco products. At the same time, they can be used in places such as ordinary grocery stores, restaurants and cafes. By 2023, the company had issued its 100,000th card, and the number of mobile application users exceeded 130,000. Practice has shown that when a Sharia-compliant financial product is introduced, customers usually transfer all their funds to halal cards and close their previously used financial products. Compliance with Sharia requirements is monitored by the international organization Shariyah Review Bureau and the Religious Affairs Office of Muslims of Kazakhstan. At the end of 2021, they signed a memorandum of cooperation, the purpose of which is not only to monitor Sharia, but also to support charitable payments such as sadaqah through a digital platform.

In recent years, the company has expanded its activities:

- In 2021, it signed a memorandum with the International Association of Islamic Business to enter the Russian market;
- In 2022, it announced an Islamic installment payment service for used cars;
- In 2023, it received the “Outstanding Digital Project in Central Asia” award at the 32nd Annual Meeting of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) in Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

Private company Alif Islamic Bank Ltd. The company received a license from the Astana International Financial Center (AIFMC) at the end of 2022 to conduct activities related to Islamic financing. Alif Islamic Bank specializes in providing capital for the development of small and medium-sized businesses on the basis of the tawarruq standard for a period of 1 to 3 years. Capital of up to 50 million tenge is provided against collateral of cars and real estate, and up to 10 million tenge is provided on an unsecured basis. According to the company's website, its Sharia Council consists of three experts. The founder of the company, N.Baybaliev, previously gained experience in business micro-finance by launching the classic microfinance organization Quantum in 2019.

Private company Kazakhstan Islamic Finance Company Ltd. There is very little information about this company. It is only known that Kazakhstan Islamic Finance Company was registered with AIFMC in September 2021. It is engaged in financing small and medium-sized businesses throughout Kazakhstan.

Propportunity is a crowdfunding platform for collective investment in real estate, founded in 2019. Through the startup, you can purchase residential or commercial real estate starting from 1 m². using four different investment funds. According to the company's founder, out of 7 thousand investors, about 500 are regular users of the platform. The platform receives commissions for transactions (2-4%) and profits (20%). The company's annual revenue is about 6 billion tenge.

The company's transformation into an Islamic bank is due to the recent interest of clients in adhering to the principles of Islamic finance. Near-term plans include obtaining an AXMM banking license and becoming an “Islamic Bank of Real Estate” in Kazakhstan. To this end, Propportunity's services are being expanded: installment payments, acquiring, deposits, account management, etc. It is also planned to launch Islamic mortgages, Islamic financial products for construction companies, and sukuk issuance. According to the latest interview of the company's founder A.Bayev, new mortgage and savings products are being introduced for investors, and a new startup was acquired to develop the Islamic ecosystem, as a result of which the business volume increased fivefold. According to the official website, a halal deposit has already been launched, which is based on real estate as collateral and promises an annual return of up to 19%. This income is formed from rental payments and an increase in the value of real estate upon resale.

Each of the organizations has certain advantages given in table 4, in particular, Tayyab has the most popular and comprehensive services in the fintech direction. Alif Islamic Bank operates under an official banking license, specializing mainly in business financing.

Proportunity differs mainly in real estate investments and halal deposits, and plans to obtain bank status in the future.

Table 4.

Institutions Providing Islamic Microfinance Services in Kazakhstan			
General Information about the Institution	Main Services	Shariah Supervision	Development Stage and Awards
Tayyab (2021, founded by D.Usonov and partners)	Digital Islamic debit cards, digital payments, money transfers; later – instalment payment services for automobiles	Shariyah Review Bureau and the Spiritual Administration of Muslims of Kazakhstan	More than 100,000 cards issued, over 130,000 mobile app users; recipient of the Outstanding Digital Project in Central Asia award
Alif Islamic Bank Ltd. (2022, MFCA license, founded by N.Baybaliev)	Financing for small and medium enterprises based on tawarruq (1-3 year capital financing)	Shariah board consisting of three experts	Newly established bank; provides secured and unsecured Islamic financing products
Kazakhstan Islamic Finance Company Ltd. (2021, MFCA registration, founded by E. Adyrakov)	Financing for small and medium enterprises	Limited information available; no public information about a Shariah board	Newly established institution; insufficient public information about its operations
Proportunity (2019, founded by A. Bayev)	Collective real estate investment (starting from 1 m ²); halal deposits, instalment plans, acquiring services, current accounts; future plans include Islamic mortgages and sukuk	Shariah supervision not fully disclosed; operates under the “halal” brand	High annual revenue, expanding business scale; plans to transform into an Islamic bank

Source: Compiled by the author based on Nagimova (2025) and official information from Tayyab, Alif Islamic Bank Ltd., Kazakhstan Islamic Finance Company Ltd. and Proportunity.

Kyrgyzstan's experience. Unlike Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Islamic microfinance market is quite diverse. *Islamic window “M Bulak”* is one of the largest microfinance organizations with a wide network in Kyrgyzstan and the CIS countries, mainly engaged in ordinary microloans. Islamic microfinance began to be provided here in 2016 through a specially created “Islamic window”. In fact, the company began developing Islamic microfinance products in 2012. Later, in 2017, “M Bulak” signed an agreement with the Islamic Development Bank (IDB) and its subsidiary ICD. It is known that at the end of 2018, this microfinance company tried to attract Turkapital from Kuwait (part of the Kuwait Finance House financial group) as a shareholder. By 2018, the company's portfolio included 13 types of Islamic financial products. Currently, the Islamic window focuses on only 5 main products: qard hasan (charitable loan of no more than 2% of the authorized capital), istisna (financing of phased production orders), ijara and ijara muntahiya bittamlik (Islamic leasing), as well as murabaha (purchase of goods with a pre-agreed price premium). According to the official website, these services are provided for a period of 3 months to 7 years, ranging from 5000 to 300000 soms.

Islamic window “Baylyk-Finans” was established in 2011 as a microcredit company, but received a license for Islamic financing only at the end of 2021. The financial statements for 2022-2023 do not reflect Islamic transactions. The company's website has a separate “Islamic Financing” section with the following conditions: the interest rate is 18-30% (depending on the term, 1-36 months), the loan amount is from 5,000

to 300,000 soms, partial early repayment is without penalty.

Bereke Finans is a small microcredit company founded in 2013. It provides term Islamic microfinance services for a period of 1 to 5 years, through participation in the capital and income of investment projects based on mudaraba and musharaka agreements. The initial authorized capital was 5 million soms, but in 2023 it was increased to 10 million soms. According to audited financial statements, the company allocated about 23 million soms to clients based on the principles of Islamic finance in 2023. Its net income after deduction of reserves in the same year exceeded 3 million soms. However, due to operating and administrative expenses and bonuses paid to employees, the company's activities ended with a loss. According to the site, the company distributes 50% of the proceeds to investors, and repayment and capitalization are carried out quarterly. The financed projects include trade, construction, manufacturing and IT companies. The company manages risks by controlling financial flows, collateral and personal guarantees. Investors' profitability has exceeded 20% in the last six months.

IslaMiKo Finans is an organization that has been operating in the Islamic microfinance market since 2022. It offers clients the following Sharia-compliant products: murabaha (purchase of goods on a fixed payment basis), istisna (production of products on an order and deferral of payment), mudaraba (share financing), as well as lease (Islamic leasing) for educational and tourism services. According to official data, financing

is short-term, from 3 to 9 months. In just one year, IslaMiKo Finans financed more than 3,200 clients in the amount of 40 million soms, and the return on capital was 99.2%.

Alif Finans has been providing Islamic micro-finance services since 2023. In its activities, it uses the following Sharia contracts: murabaha and tawarruq (for the purchase of goods), ijara and ijara muntahiya bittamlik (for the purchase of equipment and other property), istisna and parallel istisna (for custom-made production), musharaka and mudaraba, salam and parallel salam, as well as qard hasan. Individuals and business representatives can obtain financing here for up to

300,000 soms for a period of 5 to 89 months. The company's Sharia Council consists of three local experts, previously approved by the National Bank of Kyrgyzstan.

Islamic Finance Cooperative provides clients with Islamic financing services for the purchase of cars, real estate and special equipment. It has representative offices in Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan (Almaty) and Russia (Moscow, St. Petersburg). In 2022, the company signed a memorandum of understanding with the Qatari company JTA International Holding and the public organization Islamic Development Fund of Central Asia on the development of Islamic financial services.

Table 5.

Institutions Providing Islamic Microfinance Services in Kyrgyzstan

Institution (Year)	Main Products / Contracts	Financing Terms	Key Features and Outcomes
M Bulak – Islamic window (since 2016)	Qard hasan, istisna, ijara and ijara muntahiya bittamlik, murabaha	5000-300000 KGS, 3 months-7 years	Large network across CIS; partnership with IDB and ICD; previously offered 13 Islamic products, currently focused on 5 main products.
Baylyk-Finans – Islamic window (2011, license obtained end of 2021)	Murabaha-based microfinancing	5000-300000 KGS, 1-36 months, 18-30% markup	Islamic operations not reflected in 2022-2023 reports; early repayment allowed without penalty.
Bereke Finans (2013)	Mudaraba, musharaka, instalment microloans	1-5 years; charter capital increased to 10 million KGS	Provided 23 million KGS in financing in 2023; over 3 million KGS net income, but overall operations ended with a loss; investor returns above 20%.
IslaMiKo Finans (2022)	Murabaha, istisna, mudaraba, ijarah (education, tourism)	3-9 months; short-term financing	Provided over 40 million KGS to more than 3,200 clients; capital return rate 99.2%.
Alif Finans (2023)	Murabaha, tawarruq, ijarah and ijarah muntahiya bittamlik, istisna, salam, musharaka, mudaraba, qard hasan	5000-300000 KGS, 5-89 months	Widest range of Shariah-compliant products; Shariah board consists of 3 experts.
Islamic Finance Cooperative	Islamic financing for automobile, real estate, and equipment purchases	Amount and term vary (not specified on website)	Operates in Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, and Russia; signed MoU in 2022 with JTA International Holding and IDFCFA.

Source: Compiled by the author based on Nagimova (2025), the National Bank of the Kyrgyz Republic and official information from M Bulak, Baylyk-Finans, Bereke Finans, IslaMiKo Finans, Alif Finans and Islamic Finance Cooperative.

In addition to the companies considered above, according to the National Bank of Kyrgyzstan, Islamic financial services are also provided by microcredit companies Ak-Nur Kapital (since 2013) and Amin Sadek Finans (since 2021).

Islamic microfinance organizations in Kyrgyzstan operate in various areas and cover different market segments (Table 5). M Bulak, as the largest and most experienced organization, has established international cooperation, while Baylyk-Finans, despite receiving a license, has not been able to sufficiently expand Islamic

financing in its practical activities. Although Bereke Finans has entered into investment projects and provided high profitability, financial stability problems are noticeable in its overall activities. IslaMiKo Finans has shown effectiveness through short-term and high-return financing, while Alif Finans is distinguished by the widest range of Sharia products. The IFC financial cooperative operates regionally and focuses on developing international cooperation. Therefore, the experience of Kyrgyzstan shows that Islamic microfinance services are gradually developing, taking shape through the combination of different models.

Tajikistan's experience. Islamic microfinance in Tajikistan is carried out through specially created Islamic windows (Table 6). Such windows were opened on the basis of two classic microfinance companies.

Islamic window "IMON". The principles of Islamic finance began to be introduced in the microfinance company "IMON" in 2018. Soon, by decision of the Supervisory Board, an Islamic window was opened here, and in February 2020, the company was granted the right to carry out Islamic banking activities under a license from the National Bank. The company's full-fledged activities in Islamic financing began in the spring of 2020 with the introduction of the Murabaha product on the market. Under this product, "the price of the goods and the amount of the premium are necessarily disclosed to the client", which is based on the "principles of transparency and fairness". According to the official website, "IMON" has offices in two cities of Tajikistan – Khujand and Bokhtar. Here, there are murabaha and ijara services for the population, and murabaha, ijara, salam and project financing services for businesses. Interestingly, the chairman of the Sharia Council of IMON is the coordinator of the Sharia Council of the Islamic Bank "Al Hilal" in Kazakhstan and a member of the Sharia Council of "Tavhidbank" in Tajikistan, M.Shoev. In the summer of 2023, the Islamic bank "IMON" signed a Vakala agency agreement with the Project Implementation Center of the Ministry of Finance of Tajikistan and partner Islamic financial in-

stitutions within the framework of the agricultural financing project. The company's press service described this as "an important event in the development of Islamic financing in Tajikistan", since "for the first time, foreign capital for Islamic financing was provided to Islamic financial institutions". Analysis of financial statements shows that in 2023, the company's Islamic financing receivables amounted to 18.4 million somoni, which was 18% of total assets. As a result, at the end of 2023, IMON's Islamic finance portfolio was six times smaller than the receivables of the full-fledged Islamic bank in Tajikistan – Tavhidbank.

Islamic window "Humo". In 2020, an Islamic window was opened on the basis of the Humo company, one of the three leading microcredit organizations in Tajikistan. An analysis of the company's audit reports shows that over four years, receivables from Islamic financing have increased fivefold, reaching 15.6 million somoni as of the end of 2023. However, this still accounts for only 0.7% of the company's total assets. Net income from Islamic financing activities is 3.2 million somoni, which is equal to 1% of the company's net interest income or 85% of net commission income as of the end of 2022. As is known, the Humo company provides IDB funds based on the murabaha standard to farmers (up to 500 thousand somoni) and rural residents of the Khatlon region (up to 250 thousand somoni), for a period of 3 to 36 months, with an annual interest rate of 10%.

Table 6. Institutions Providing Islamic Microfinance Services in Tajikistan

Institution	Main Islamic Products	Financing Scale / Shariah Governance	Key Features & Outcomes
IMON – Islamic Window (Islamic finance since 2018; Islamic banking license in 2020)	Murabaha, ijara, salam, project financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Islamic financing receivables: 18.4 million TJS (18% of assets, 2023) Shariah Council chaired by M.Shoev (also on Al Hilal Bank & Tavhidbank boards) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offices in Khujand and Bokhtar First full-fledged Islamic operations began in 2020 Signed Vakala agency agreement in 2023 to attract foreign Islamic capital Islamic portfolio remains smaller than Tavhidbank (6 times difference)
Humo – Islamic Window (opened 2020)	Murabaha (IDB-funded), ijara	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing limits: farmers up to 500000 TJS, rural households up to 250000 TJS Terms: 3-36 months, 10% annual markup Islamic financing receivables: 15.6 million TJS (0.7% of assets, 2023) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receivables grew fivefold (2020-2023) Net income from Islamic financing: 3.2 million TJS (1% of net interest income; 85% of net commission income, 2022) One of Tajikistan's largest microcredit institutions

Source: Compiled by the author based on Nagimova (2025), official information from IMON International and Humo, and their financial statements for 2022-2023.

Uzbekistan's experience. In recent years, a number of local banks ("Ipak Yuli", "Qishloq Qurilish Bank", "Agrobank", "Turonbank", "Trastbank", "Kapitalbank", "Asia-Alliance Bank", "O'zbekiston Xalq Banki") have been preparing to establish Islamic windows, but in practice this process is limited to episodic attraction of funds by the IDB.

The Board of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, by its resolution No. 23/4 dated July 19, 2024, approved the Regulation "On the Procedure for the Provision of Islamic Financing Services by Microfinance Organizations". According to this regulation,

each microfinance organization providing Islamic finance services is required to establish a "special council for coordinating Islamic finance issues" (Sharia supervisory board) or may involve it on a contractual (outsourcing) basis. In this case, the microfinance organization is considered responsible for managing all risks associated with the activities of the special council to which it is involved.

In 2024, microfinance organizations were first allowed to provide Islamic finance services. The regulation on this activity allows them to provide services using Islamic finance instruments and mechanisms such

as murabaha, ijara (Islamic lease), salam, musharaka and mudaraba (Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024). During August-December 2024, resources

in the amount of almost 1.1 billion soums were allocated through microfinance organizations (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Volume of Islamic Finance Services Provided by Microfinance Organizations (in million UZS)

Source: Compiled by the author based on the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2024).

Today, several microfinance organizations providing Islamic finance services are operating in Uzbekistan.

The microfinance organization “Apex Moliya” LLC was registered on February 6, 2024, and the authorized capital of the organization is 2 billion soums. This microfinance institution offers a range of financial

products based on Sharia principles in its activities. In particular, it is reported that it uses instruments such as murabaha, ijara, salam, mudaraba and musharaka.

The Islamic finance products offered by this organization have a term of 6 to 60 months, and the rate of return is set in the range of 20-30% (Table 7).

Table 7.

Islamic Finance Products Offered by “APEX MOLLIYA” LLC Microfinance Organization				
Product	Profitability	Down Payment	Term (months)	Minimum Amount
Murabaha	20-25%	0-30%	6-60	5000000 UZS
Ijara	20-25%	0-30%	13-60	5000000 UZS
Salam	20-25%	0%	6-60	5000000 UZS
Mudaraba	20-25%	0%	6-60	5000000 UZS
Musharaka	25-30%	0%	6-60	5000000 UZS

Source: Compiled by the author based on official information from “Apex Moliya” LLC.

“The microfinance organization “Apex Moliya” has formed a special council – Sharia Council, consisting of international and local specialists in order to organize its activities in accordance with the principles of Sharia. The council includes experts with experience in the fields of Islamic law, finance and economics. The main task of this council is to monitor the compliance of the organization’s financial products (murabaha, ijara, salam, mudaraba, musharaka) with Sharia norms, issue fatwas and advice.

“ANSOR MMT” LLC was established in 2024. The main feature of the organization is the provision of microfinance services that are fully compliant with the principles of Sharia.

Main financial products:

- Murabaha – purchase of goods and their future sale with a premium.
- Ijara / Ijara muntahiya bittamlik – lease of movable and immovable property with the right to purchase it later.
- Mudaraba – raising funds on a partnership basis and distributing profits and losses on a contractual basis.
- Musharaka – capital partnership, profit and loss sharing according to the participants’ share.

- Salam – financing based on prepayment for the product and subsequent delivery.

Special Council: A special council has been established under “ANSOR MMT” to ensure Sharia-compliant activities. The members of the council are specialists with deep knowledge and experience in the fields of Islamic finance, banking and finance, accounting, auditing and valuation.

Here, it is worth mentioning another market participant providing Islamic microfinance services. IMAN is an Islamic fintech project that connects sellers, buyers and investors based on the principles of Islamic finance. The project was founded in 2018 and was fully launched in 2020. Today, it operates through two mobile applications: IMAN Invest, which allows investing based on the principles of Islamic finance, and IMAN Pay, which allows residents of Uzbekistan to purchase goods on an installment basis using funds raised through IMAN Invest.

IMAN Invest is globally focused (according to the company, residents of more than 60 countries are investors), while IMAN Pay currently serves only residents of Uzbekistan. According to the company’s founder: “We see ourselves as a super-app that meets the needs of Muslims for international payments, in-

stant money transfers, micro investments, micro-finance, instant education and many other digital products”.

According to IMAN’s reports for the first quarter of 2022, the Islamic term payment portfolio exceeded 21 billion soums, the number of borrowers was 3400 people; the investment portfolio reached almost 17 billion soums, and the number of investors exceeded 1400 people. Also, through the platform, every citizen has the opportunity to become an investor starting from 1 million soums (about 80 USD). During this period, the net profit margin was 19%, and the largest expense was the scoring system (more than 130 million soums).

According to the company’s founder, R.Rakhmatov, 10 employees worked on the initial product, and now the team consists of 60 people, half of whom are IT specialists. At first, the project was financed with its own funds and “small angel investments” (200 thousand USD), and later 1 million USD was raised from eight venture funds in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and the United States. At the beginning of 2022, another 1 million USD was raised from investors in Kazakhstan, Singapore and the United States as part of a new round.

According to the company’s future plans, IMAN will be launched in Kazakhstan, and later it is planned to enter the markets of Pakistan, Bangladesh, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia and the United States.

FINDINGS

The findings show that Islamic microfinance is developing in different countries under the influence of specific legal, institutional, economic and technological conditions. Although the basic Shariah principles are common, the effectiveness, financial sustainability and social coverage of Islamic microfinance models differ significantly across countries. These differences are mainly related to the regulatory framework, the quality of Shariah governance, the level of integration with social finance institutions and the use of digital financial technologies.

The Malaysian experience demonstrates that the sustainable development of Islamic microfinance requires a strong legal framework, systematic Shariah supervision and close integration with social finance mechanisms such as zakat and waqf. The dual-channel model used in Malaysia shows that the combination of commercial finance and social finance can strengthen both financial sustainability and social impact. Pakistan’s experience confirms that state-supported guidelines, tax incentives and the active participation of non-profit institutions can play an important role in expanding Islamic microfinance. In particular, the Akhuwat model shows that interest-free financing based on social solidarity can achieve high repayment discipline and positive social outcomes.

The Indonesian model is mainly based on decentralized Islamic rural banks. BPRS institutions have become an important mechanism for supporting small business, agriculture and regional entrepreneurship. Their experience shows that Islamic microfinance can be more effective when it is adapted to local economic needs and supported by trust-based relationships with clients. At the same time, the gradual expansion of digital services creates additional opportunities for increasing outreach and operational efficiency.

The experience of Central Asian countries shows that Islamic microfinance is developing unevenly across the region. In Kazakhstan, Islamic microfinance is expanding mainly through fintech projects and new market-oriented Islamic finance institutions. In Kyrgyzstan, the sector is more diversified, with Islamic windows, microfinance companies and cooperative models operating in parallel. However, some institutions still face challenges related to Shariah governance, institutional stability and transparency. In Tajikistan, Islamic microfinance is at an early stage and is mainly developing through Islamic windows within existing microfinance institutions. The examples of IMON and Humo show that the share of Islamic finance in total assets remains limited, although the range of services is gradually expanding.

The results for Uzbekistan show that the regulatory changes adopted in 2024 created an important legal basis for the practical introduction of Islamic financial services in microfinance organizations. The activities of “Apex Moliya”, “Ansor MMT” and the fintech platform “IMAN” indicate that initial market demand exists and that Shariah-compliant microfinance products can become an important part of the national financial system. At the same time, the current stage of development remains initial, and the sector requires further institutional strengthening.

The analysis identifies three key conditions for the sustainable development of Islamic microfinance in Uzbekistan. First, unified standards for Shariah-compliant microfinance products and Shariah governance should be developed. This is necessary to increase transparency, reduce regulatory uncertainty and strengthen public trust. Second, the capital base of Islamic microfinance organizations should be diversified through the gradual integration of social finance instruments such as zakat, waqf and sadaqah. Third, risk management mechanisms should be improved through digital technologies, scoring systems and better monitoring of financing operations.

Overall, the study confirms that Islamic microfinance can contribute to financial inclusion, small entrepreneurship development and social justice in Uzbekistan. International experience shows that the success of this sector depends not only on the formal permission to provide Islamic financial services, but also on the quality of regulation, institutional trust, Shariah compliance, access to sustainable funding sources and technological capacity. Therefore, the systematic development of Islamic microfinance should be considered an important strategic direction for expanding inclusive and value-based financial services in Uzbekistan.

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